

The Effects on Turkey of the Intra Struggles Delineated Mainly on Oil, by the Members of the Western World: how should we cope with it?

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Abstract

Commercial and energy tensions and *intra struggles* of i) US on the one side of the Atlantic Ocean, ii) England, France and Germany on the other side, i.e. altogether, the Western world, embodying Japan as well, taking place on the platforms of Europe, and the Middle East, are undoubtedly reflected upon Turkey and her neighboring region, no matter how fierce or smooth. Turkey and the region, amongst other things, suffer of these. A path to be followed by Turkey, to insure security, politically and defense-wise, is discussed. The recent and hot counter interventions of Russian Federation, Iran, even further Republic of China, no doubt made the situation in the region even worse, and requires a special attention, and will be dealt with elsewhere.

Keywords: Defense, Intra Struggles, Middle East, Oil, Turkey, Western World.

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1. Introduction

In this article, we will consider mainly *intra struggles* of i) US on the one side of the Atlantic Ocean, ii) England, France and Germany on the other side, i.e. altogether, the Western world, embodying Japan as well, that take place on the platforms of Europe, and the Middle East, along with their reflections upon Turkey and her neighboring region, no matter how fierce or smooth. Turkey and the region, amongst other things, suffer of these. We thusly discuss the essentials to be followed by Turkey, to insure security, politically and defense-wise.

The recent and hot counter interventions of Russian Federation, Iran, even further Republic of China, no doubt made the situation in the region even worse, and requires a special attention, which we will deal with, elsewhere.

Nonetheless these do not alter in any way the essentials brought up in here.

2. Development and explanation

2.1. Effects of US-EU-Far East Relations on Turkey

The interaction between the world powers and Turkey can be schematized, as follows.

The EU witnesses historically anticipated tensions between the three super powers of Europe, England France and Germany, as to which will be the future leader of the Union. England, at this race seemed to have lost her chance, not only that she is not a country of the old continent, but also at this point, she appears totally embarked with the US.

In any case, on the continent, there are “commercial tensions’ rising from relations of the US especially with France and Germany.

Tensions between the US and the EU based on NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) will be mentioned later.

‘Commercial tensions’ being witnessed between the European Powers, Japan and Far Eastern producers on the European market, are as well to be considered.

Furthermore, we must not skip the ‘competition’ between the US, Japan and Far Eastern producers, on European markets.

Finally and most important, France and Germany on the one hand, and the US and England on the other hand, seek to enlarge their hinterland and possible access to oil, through a veiled, but severe war against each other.

It would be naive to assume that such contrast and tension would have no reflections on Turkey.

Thus, we must agree upon the fact that:

The above mentioned tensions and intra struggles of the Western world (Japan as well included), are undoubtedly reflected upon Turkey and her neighboring region no matter how fierce or smooth.

One interesting example to this is the “terrorist” PKK, i.e. (the non-existent) “Kurdistan, Workers’ Party (whatever names she would have assumed afterwards). During the heydays of the PKK terror, Western Powers who sold to Turkey Cobra choppers, interestingly enough donated the PKK, as well, with many opportunities as well as many a weaponry such as missiles.

Thus, it seems that our so-called allies (anyway “allies”, so to say, in between themselves), have not only been insincere to us, but struggled with each other as well.

Thus, it appears no longer clear whether it was we who fought against the terrorist PKK, or it was them who fought against each other, over seemingly the PKK against Turkey.

Similarly the fact that the West and especially Germany in matters of “Yugoslavia”, had had interest in the creation of a hinterland for herself through locally provoked tensions. The fact that Germany provocations laid in the basis of the violence witnessed in the Balkans topped with the Bosnia-Herzegovina sabotage, was what the Serbian leader Radovan Karajitz had claimed in person. Yet, it is as well true that the USA has by no means held back as it intervened and took its privileged part in

the region's struggle by means of the NATO, inevitably induced by the Serbia-Russian alliance.

Similarly, no European country has considered the Caucasian, the Armenian or the Azerbaijani disputes which gulped even Russia in as being uninteresting. Thus, it is all so possible to say that even these events were not out of the European intra struggle for a hinterland.

Finally, it seems bitterly attractive trying to anticipate the US intervention on Afghanistan as it surely leads to internal struggles and disputes in the West, no matter to what degree the Western world, including Russia, seems allied on the matter.

By around 2000, Turkish Armed Forces had, all at once won a hard battle against the terrorism and as well against the West and the US interest in acquiring a hinterland in the region. To put it simpler, it would be wiser to say that the Turkish nation as one corps, the Turkish Republic, by then appeared to be the real victor of the matter, until though the US invaded Iraq in 2003, and promoted openly or less openly the establishment of a Kurdish state in the Northern Iraq (naturally aiming to get broadened toward the South East of Turkey, East of Syria and West of Iran), after which terrorism against Turkey (no doubt with the support of the Westerners), seems nowadays once again, activated.

Recall yet that, in the last round of the matter in 1999, as the US, who initially had worked for the benefit of the PKK, has in the last instance swerved and had been a helping hand for Turkey in capturing the terrorist PKK leader A. Ocalan (merely the cap of the pack) in Africa, has 'fixed', stabilized in a way, her attitudes towards the remaining powers of the West, she became to be the other benefactor of the situation whereas the European West in the quest for a hinterland has failed.³

³ We must hereby underline that we have no intention of claiming that the PKK was just a European provocation. Considering the PKK, it would be wise to look for the traces of these two principal factors:

i) whether there is any who provoked, and
ii) whether there is an inherently mechanism, easy to be provoked. Thus, it is clear that in matters of the provoked and the provoker, the presence of one without the other is not mandatory.

In other words, not putting aside the internal dynamics, evidently, if we were nevertheless asked to summarize the PKK terrorism in only one sentence, here is what we would say:

- The western world's main actors, the essential reason being oil, fought against each other, over the PKK.

If we were asked to state just one more sentence, here is what we would add:

- The US defeated Europe (not including England) in the region, and expelled her from the Middle East.

Here is a plain third fact.

- PKK now is a card, The US (for the time being, the only western actor in the region), can play not only against Turkey, but against even Syria and Iran who ironically, had supported this malformation against Turkey, though they fight nowadays on the case, against, USA, seemingly together with Russian Federation and the Republic of China.

It would be fair to recall that the foregoing analysis had been made by the authors, already by 2005.

3. Internal Stability: A Basic Solution

Turkey is a crucial crossroads on the modern silk road that leads to the petrol and the natural gas reserves of the Middle and the Far East.

On the other hand, Turkey is as well to be considered as one important station on the passageway that leads the US and Europe to the Turkic Republics and the Far East and vice versa.

Thus, we obviously have many reasons to be burdened with.

What needs immediately to be done for and by Turkey then is to ensure at first hand, the internal stability. Yet, instead of preaching brotherhood and unity, elimination of the social inequities would be by far sane and sound.

There is no need to look for reasons of threat and insecurity afar when the distribution of incomes is so corrupted and unjust; even speaking of a "nation" in such a case appears to be irrelevant.

When we fail to be “the nation”, foes would all so naturally try to benefit from our feebleness.

4. Internal Polarizations of Structural Transformations, and the Quest of Nationality

In relation with Turkey's position as the principal crossroads between the Eastern and the Western markets, a huge American enterprise, for example, would engage with one huge Turkish holding and another German giant on the other hand would cooperate again with another great Turkish holding, leading to a polarization of two foreign states on Turkish territory, inevitably opposing two Turkish companies.

Such situation clearly states that Turkey (just like, no doubt any other developing, and whatever it means, “globalizing” country) as well, takes her share of some international struggle for commerce as when two national companies oppose the bitter question nationality is raised.

In other words, all the above mentioned tensions, commercial dogfight and provoked terror topped with our internal instabilities leads to the corruption of our notion of nationality.

5. The US-EU Dispute and Turkey

The US-EU dispute dates back to the 1960s. The transmission of the NATO headquarters from Paris to Brussels by the World War II Victor France of General de Gaulle gave the dispute its cutting age. No more historical details will be given here yet as NATO was surely the basic military apparatus of the West during the Cold War years, any possible dispute between the USA and Europe were in a way, postponed.

The Cold War initially ended in favor of the US yet by the collapse of the shared enemy, the Soviet Union. There by Europe no longer needed neither the US nor the NATO. Thus, the US would have no chance in becoming the master of Europe.

As the US is unhappy with such outcome, she tried to pull the EU more and more into NATO who is by then, looking for newer definitions and missions for itself, possibly forced by the inner oppositions of Europe. As the NATO family gets crowded, the

presences of Germany and especially France in the organization are tried to lessen would be much more suitable a statement.

Further, although Europe is not prone immediately to become the United States of Europe, she is already politically, monetarily and commercially united, leaving behind the military and defense industry unions.

It must be emphasized that the union of European defense industries, being much more crucial than any military union, is the integral essence of the latter.

Although a minor possibility, no matter how 'integrated' a ‘multi-focused’ European defense industry would evolve, it would still be far from competing with the giant American defense industry; the internal competition within nations being another default.

Yet, Europe still appears to be considering a military union more than ever, outside of NATO, no matter how many preceding attempts have failed.

Thus is the present dispute.

The US on the other hand seems to have no choice other than what she has forever been trying: Forcing the EU more and more into the NATO, eliminating the outstanding independent European powers in such expanded NATO thus, claiming her force on the EU and to impede the EU wish for a military union.

Thus, it is clear that the US counter attacks on the Independent Military Union of Europe, in one way or another, aim either at the nullification of similar attempts through various stages of the NATO apparatus or at acquiring authority.

Ironically it seems that the US would even embrace as her principal stratagem the continuation of the cold war as a shield against troubles she would be faced with the European crisis which gets even more chronic every day!

Back to Turkey, we see that Turkey holds no chance for membership to the EU in near future. It must be underlined that agreement on the Customs Union was thus not beneficial for Turkey within the present situation. Within this framework, Turkey seems to have no preference between the US and the EU.

The US-EU polarization is thus, a crucial situation.

Turkey would behave wiser in case she manages successfully, harmoniously, rationally and decidedly to keep at equal distances to

- the US who has always seen her as a border station, a surveillance post, a military base,
- the EU who has always preferred a suspicious, a hesitant attitude towards her,
- Russia, no matter what has been the yield of the Cold War years, and
- other major and minor powers,

as she also internally

- reinforces her stability and social solidarity, the key ingredient of behaving as a nation, and
- conducts herself realistically, and with individuality.

As defense industry is an integral part of defense and moreover, power, we feel the urge to speak a bit of the establishment of a rational defense industry which we consider Turkey, although she now sympathizes with, to have delayed and averred so far in order to fulfill the requirements of our subject.

One must never forget (not to mention the dramatic fact of donation of arms) that if one country is armed with foreign weaponry in today's world, even though she has purchased her arms, she would one day find herself fighting for the producer of those weapons.

Thus, considering Turkey as an ally for the protection of both regional and global peace, establishment of a realistic and rationalistic a defense industry is inevitably crucial.

Following, are the principal theorems we consider 'requisite' under such conditions.

6. A Developing Country's Defense Industry

Turkish defense industry, or in fact any Developing Country's Defense Industry, should comply with the following, if it wishes to be rationalistic, realistic and national; thus it should be: [1]

- an integral part of civil industry, supplied by the civil industry, supply and develop the civil industry,

- not producing irrelevant arms, but be integrated within itself,
- national, i.e., nationally manufactured, not foreign licensed and not purchased under any mandatory condition.
- Note that we are not talking about "defense", but "defense industry".

The Turkish defense industry should as well comply with the first three of the above conditions if it wishes not to be a burden to the Turkish economy, and also it should comply with the last if it wishes the usage of the product in question, to be effective.

Another crucially important theorem for the mentioned conditions is that the defense industry of one such country as Turkey should not immediately aim at the production of related technologies, from scratch. Yes, this must be perhaps set as a final aim. Yet, unlike the Project F-16 [Project on the Production of General Dynamics Air Combat Fighter in Turkey], to start with "small product" development must be aimed at.

Talking of the development of the defense industry, production of defensive weapons (anti-tanks) instead of attack weapons (tanks) is what should be aimed at order for the industry in itself may find means of self-development.

As weapons of attack would be obtained when need be, what we consider to be the most profitable approach is the production of defensive weapons.

7. Conclusions

Technology may sometimes be ignored during strategical analyses. Yet, one thing is for certain that a Turkey of strategical importance can only be the one which has managed to establish her own defense industry as the ability to defend oneself is from now on measured by the abilities of one's defense industry.

Civil participation to the strategical aim planning's of the General Staff concerning the plans for strategical technologies and defense industries is as vital as the defense industry budgets having no matter how grand or small shares given to the development of the national defense industry during arms supplies.

Thus, it would be possible for Turkey to realize her above mentioned mission, under all circumstances.

The recent and hot counter interventions of Russian Federation, Iran, even further Republic of China, no doubt made the situation in the region, even worse, and requires a special attention, which we will deal with, elsewhere. Nonetheless these do not alter in any way the essentials brought up in here.

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